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Research Article

**AWARENESS AND PERCEPTION OF INTRAVENOUS
THROMBOLYSIS FOR ACUTE ISCHEMIC STROKE AMONG
THE GENERAL POPULATION IN TAIF CITY, SAUDI ARABIA.****Naif Edah Alomairi**Department of internal medicine, college of medicine, Taif university, Taif 21944 , Saudi Arabia,
Neurology Consultant, Alhada Armed Forces Hospital, Taif, Saudi Arabia.**Abstract:**

Background: Stroke ranks as the second leading cause of dementia and death globally. Despite the established effectiveness of tissue plasminogen activator (tPA) in treating ischemic stroke, its use remains limited worldwide.

Objectives: This study evaluates the awareness, knowledge, and attitudes of adults regarding stroke symptoms, thrombolytic therapy for acute ischemic stroke (AIS), and the critical treatment window.

Materials and Methods: Conducted in Taif, Saudi Arabia, from March to April 2024, this cross-sectional study involved 272 Saudi adults aged 18-60 years, selected through a convenience sampling method. Data collection was done via a self-administered online questionnaire in Arabic, which included demographic details, personal or family history of AIS, knowledge about stroke, and sources of information.

Results: Participants were mainly aged 36-55 years (43%) and female (67.4%). A personal or family history of AIS was reported by 44.1%. About 52.9% demonstrated sufficient knowledge of stroke and thrombolytic therapy. Family and friends (42.3%) and the internet and social media (40.4%) were the main information sources. Logistic regression indicated that using newspapers/medical magazines and information from family/friends were linked to significantly better knowledge (AOR=0.13, CI: 0.01-0.42, p=0.002 and AOR=0.34, CI: 0.12-0.96, p=0.041, respectively). Having multiple sources of information significantly reduced the risk of insufficient knowledge (AOR=0.06, CI: 0.02-0.19, p<0.001 and AOR=0.15, CI: 0.05-0.49, p=0.002).

Conclusion: The general population in Taif has adequate knowledge of stroke symptoms and thrombolytic therapy, but gaps remain in recognizing some symptoms and the critical time window for tPA administration.

Keywords: Stroke, Thrombolysis, Time window, Knowledge, General population.

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INTRODUCTION:

Globally, cerebrovascular accidents (strokes) rank as the second leading cause of dementia and mortality [1]. Despite the established efficacy of tissue plasminogen activator (tPA) in the treatment of ischemic stroke [2], its administration remains limited, with only 3-5% of acute ischemic stroke (AIS) patients receiving this intervention worldwide [3,6].

The administration of tPA within a 4.5-hour window from the onset of AIS symptoms is strongly recommended to optimize patient outcomes [7]. Consequently, it is imperative for patients exhibiting AIS symptoms to promptly reach hospitals equipped to administer rt-PA [8].

Several factors contribute to the underutilization of tPA, including a lack of public awareness about the early symptoms and signs of AIS and the importance of timely intervention. Additionally, the complexity of implementing effective stroke care plans and the delayed adoption of best practices at the community level further impede timely treatment [9,10]. Enhancing awareness of thrombolytic therapy for AIS, particularly its critical time window, could lead to earlier management and reduce pre-hospitalization delays [11].

On a global scale, while tPA therapy is available in most public hospitals, its suboptimal utilization is often attributed to insufficient knowledge and inadequate practice among healthcare providers [12]. Many physicians express concerns regarding the potential adverse effects associated with thrombolytic therapy, particularly intracranial haemorrhage [13].

Barriers to the use of tPA by physicians include perceived lack of documented efficacy, insufficient expertise in stroke management, and medicolegal concerns [14]. This apprehensive attitude among healthcare providers can influence patients and their caregivers, leading to resistance against the utilization of tPA therapy in AIS [15].

This study was conducted in Taif, the western region in Saudi Arabia and aimed to evaluate the awareness, knowledge, and attitudes of the general adult population regarding the early signs and symptoms of stroke, the availability of thrombolytic therapy for AIS, and the critical time window for its administration.

Patients and methods:

A population-based cross-sectional study was conducted in Taif city, located in the western region of Saudi Arabia within Makkah Province, with an estimated population of 717,334 (2024 estimated census) [16].

The study population included all Saudi adults aged 18-60 years of both genders residing in Taif city during the data collection period (March-April 2024).

Exclusion criteria:

- Individuals younger than 18 years or older than 60 years,
- those who were severely ill,

The sample size was calculated using the following formula for estimating population-based sample size [17]:

$$N = \frac{Z_{\alpha/2}^2 \times p(1-p)}{D^2}$$

Where: n=Minimum sample size
 $Z_{\alpha/2}$: the critical value of the Normal distribution at $\alpha/2$ (e.g. for a confidence level of 95%, α is 0.05 and the critical value is 1.96)

Thus, the calculated minimum sample size was:

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.23 \times 0.77}{(0.05)^2} = 272$$

A non-probability convenience sampling technique was employed, and the developed questionnaire was distributed via Google Forms.

Data were collected using a self-administered Arabic online questionnaire adapted from a similar study recently conducted in China by Young et al [11].

The questionnaire comprised four main sections:

1. Demographic characteristics (age, gender, nationality, educational level, and employment status).
2. Personal and/or family history of AIS.
3. Knowledge about stroke and its thrombolytic therapy (three multiple-choice questions).

Correct answers were assigned a score of 1, and incorrect answers were assigned a score of 0. The total score was computed, and its median value was identified.

Participants scoring below the median value were considered to have "insufficient knowledge," whereas those scoring at or above the median value were considered to have "sufficient knowledge."

4. Sources of information about stroke with allowable multiple responses.

The questionnaire was translated into Arabic and then retranslated into English to ensure accuracy. The validity of the resultant Arabic questionnaire was confirmed by three neurology consultants from Al-Hada Armed Forces Hospital in Taif City and the College of Medicine at Taif University.

Ethical approval:

Approval for the research proposal was obtained from the Scientific Research Ethics Committee at Taif University, Taif, Saudi Arabia. Online individual consent was required from each participant prior to data collection. Letter number: 45-250 dated / 2024-03-19

Statistical analysis:

Appropriate descriptive and analytical statistical methods and tests were conducted using SPSS version

28 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY, USA). A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered the threshold for significance throughout the study.

RESULTS:

Demographic Characteristics

- A total of 272 participants were included in the study. The majority (43%) fell within the age range of 36 to 55 years.
- Females constituted 67.4% of the participants, with Saudi nationals comprising 96.3% of the sample.
- Educational attainment was relatively high, with 80.5% of participants holding bachelor's or postgraduate degrees.
- Employment status varied, with governmental employees representing 33.3% of the participants, and 28.7% identified as students. (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic characteristics of the participants (n=272)

	Frequency	Percentage
Age in years		
18-35	92	33.8
36-55	117	43.0
>55	63	23.2
Gender		
Male	86	31.6
Female	186	68.4
Nationality		
Saudi	262	96.3
Non-Saudi	10	3.7
Educational level		
Intermediate-Secondary schools	53	19.5
Bachelor/postgraduate	219	80.5
Employment status		
Not working/housewife	18	6.6
Governmental employee	108	39.7
Private sector employee	16	5.9
Retired	52	19.1
Students	78	28.7

Medical History:

- 44.1% of participants reported a personal or family history of acute ischemic stroke. (Figure 1).

Figure 1: History of having personal or family history of acute ischemic stroke among the participants.

Recognition of Stroke and Thrombolytic Therapy:

- 62.5% of participants identified thrombolytic agents as appropriate treatment for cerebral infarction.
- Only 41.2% were aware of the optimal time frame (4-5 hours post-onset) for administering thrombolytic therapy. (Table 2/Figure 2).

Knowledge Levels

- Overall, 52.9% of participants demonstrated sufficient knowledge about stroke and intravenous thrombolysis. (Figure 2).
- Sudden difficulty in speaking, understanding, or slurred speech ranked first, followed by sudden numbness or weakness of the face and/or limb(s) on one side of the body
- The most recognized sudden severe headache with unknown cause is not one of the warning signs of stroke (74.3%). (Table 2).

Table 2: Responses of the participants to knowledge questions about stroke and intravenous thrombolysis in patients with acute ischemic stroke.

Questions	Correct answers		
	Response	Frequency	Percentage
What kind of drug should be used to treat someone who is suffering from cerebral infarction	Thrombolytic agent	170	62.5
Within how much time after a stroke begins this drug needs to be given to be effective?	Within 4-5 hours after stroke onset	112	41.2
Which of the following are among the warning signs of stroke -Sudden difficulty in speaking, understanding, or slurred speech -Sudden blurred vision in one or both eyes -Sudden severe headache with unknown cause -Sudden dizziness, difficulty in walking, loss of balance or co-ordination - Sudden numbness or weakness of the face and/or limb(s) on one side of the body	Yes	189	69.5
	Yes	84	30.9
	No	202	74.3
	Yes	85	31.3
	Yes	181	66.5

Figure 2: Overall knowledge about stroke and intravenous thrombolysis in patients with acute ischemic stroke among the participants

Sources of Information:

- The primary sources of information about stroke were family, friends, and relatives (42.3%), followed closely by internet/social media (40.4%).
- Healthcare professionals were cited by 22.8% of participants as a source of information. (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Sources of information about stroke among the participants (Not mutually exclusive i.e. sum may exceed 100%).

Factors Associated with Knowledge:

- Subgroup analysis revealed that younger participants (18-35 years) exhibited greater knowledge about stroke and intravenous thrombolysis compared to older individuals (>55 years) (68.5% vs. 47.6%, $p=0.001$).
- Participants with lower levels of education demonstrated higher levels of knowledge compared to those with higher education (66% vs. 49.8%, $p=0.033$).

- Students displayed the highest rate of sufficient knowledge (70.5%) compared to housewives and unemployed participants, who exhibited the lowest rates (33.3%, $p=0.003$).
- Participants who obtained information from newspapers or medical magazines demonstrated significantly higher knowledge levels compared to those without any such source ($p<0.001$). (Table 3).

Table 3: Factors associated with knowledge of the participants about stroke and intravenous thrombolysis in patients with acute ischemic stroke.

	Knowledge about intravenous thrombolysis in patients with acute ischemic stroke		p-value*
	Insufficient N=128 N (%)	Sufficient N=144 N (%)	
Age in years			
18-35 (n=92)	29 (31.5)	63 (68.5)	0.001
36-55 (n=117)	66 (56.4)	51 (43.6)	
>55 (n=53)	33 (52.4)	30 (47.6)	
Gender			
Male (n=86)	45 (52.3)	41 (47.7)	0.237
Female (n=186)	83 (44.6)	103 (55.4)	
Nationality			
Saudi (n=262)	122 (46.6)	140 (53.4)	0.403
Non-Saudi (n=10)	6 (60.0)	4 (40.0)	
Educational level			
Intermediate/Secondary schools (n=53)	18 (34.0)	35 (66.0)	0.033
Bachelor/Postgraduate (n=219)	110 (50.2)	109 (49.8)	
Employment status			
Not working/Housewife (n=18)	12 (66.7)	6 (33.3)	0.003
Governmental employee (n=108)	60 (55.6)	48 (44.4)	
Private sector employee (n=16)	7 (43.8)	9 (56.3)	
Retired (n=52)	26 (50.0)	26 (50.0)	
Students (n=78)	23 (29.5)	55 (70.5)	
History of having personal or family history of acute ischemic stroke			
No (n=152)	70 (46.1)	82 (53.9)	0.708
Yes (n=120)	58 (48.3)	62 (51.7)	
Sources of information about stroke			
No (n=25)			<0.001
Television/Radio (n=18)	19 (76.0)	6 (24.0)	
Internet/Social media (n=50)	16 (88.9)	2 (11.1)	
Newspapers/Medical magazines (n=9)	30 (60.0)	20 (40.0)	
Healthcare professionals (n=14)	0 (0.0)	9 (100)	
Family/Friends/Relatives (n=73)			
Two sources (n=52)	7 (50.0)	7 (50.0)	
More than two sources (n=31)	38 (52.0)	35 (47.9)	
	8 (15.4)	44 (84.6)	
	10 (32.3)	21 (67.7)	

Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis:

- Source of information was significantly associated with knowledge levels about stroke and intravenous thrombolysis. Participants who received information from newspapers or medical magazines were at significantly lower risk of insufficient knowledge compared to those without any such source (Adjusted Odds Ratio [AOR]=0.13, 95% Confidence Intervals [CI]: 0.01-0.42, p=0.002). (Table 4).

Table 4: Predictors of insufficient knowledge about intravenous thrombolysis in patients with acute ischemic stroke: Results of multivariate logistic regression analysis

	Adjusted odds ratio	95% confidence interval	p-value
Sources of information about stroke			
No ^a	1.0		
Television/Radio	2.53	0.45-14.29	0.295
Internet/Social media	0.47	0.16-1.39	0.174
Newspapers/Medical magazines	0.13	0.01-0.42	0.002
Healthcare professionals			
Family/Friends/Relatives	0.32	0.08-1.27	0.105
Two sources	0.34	0.12-0.96	0.041
More than two sources	0.06	0.02-0.19	<0.001
	0.15	0.05-0.49	0.002

^a: Reference category

Terms of age, employment status and educational status were removed from the final logistic regression model (Not significant).

DISCUSSION:

Recent guidelines underscore the paramount importance of administering tissue plasminogen activator (tPA) within a narrow 4.5-hour window following the onset of stroke symptoms to optimize the prognosis of Acute Ischemic Stroke (AIS).

Despite these recommendations, the utilization rates of tPA remain suboptimal due to various factors, including insufficient awareness among both the general population and healthcare practitioners regarding the urgency of recognizing stroke symptoms promptly and initiating thrombolytic therapy [18]. Therefore, a thorough exploration of public knowledge concerning early stroke symptoms, thrombolytic agents, and the time frame for their administration is essential to enhance treatment outcomes. Notably, there is a lack of similar studies conducted within the general population of Saudi Arabia on this critical subject matter.

In the present study, 62.5% of participants recognized thrombolytic agents as essential drugs for treating cerebral infarction, while 41.2% were aware of the crucial 4-5-hour time window post-stroke onset for effective administration as shown in table 2 Overall, more than half of the participants demonstrated a satisfactory level of knowledge regarding stroke and intravenous thrombolysis in AIS patients as shown in Fig 2 /Table 2 .

It is noteworthy that previous studies predominantly focused on emergency physicians [12,14], with only a few examining the general population. For instance, a study conducted in the United States in 2009 revealed

that approximately one-third of respondents (32.2%) were aware of tPA as a treatment for acute stroke, with 52.7% recognizing the necessity of its administration within 3 hours of symptom onset [8]. Similarly, a study in China in 2014 reported that less than a quarter of respondents (23.3%) were aware of thrombolytic therapy for AIS, with 59.9% possessing knowledge of the appropriate time window [11].

The current study identified a significant association between the source of information and the level of knowledge concerning stroke and intravenous thrombolysis as shown in table 3 /fig.3 Participants who accessed information from newspapers/medical magazines or from family members, friends, or relatives, as well as those who relied on multiple sources, exhibited higher levels of knowledge compared to those without any specific information source. In contrast, variable results were observed in analogous studies conducted in the USA and China. In the USA, middle-aged individuals, females, Caucasians, higher-educated adults, and those with higher income demonstrated greater awareness regarding tPA, with middle-aged white adults displaying better knowledge of the treatment's time window [8]. Conversely, in China, younger individuals, the more educated, those with health insurance, higher income brackets, and those able to recognize all five warning signs of stroke exhibited higher awareness of thrombolytic therapy, while the elderly (≥ 75 years) displayed better knowledge of the treatment's time window [11].

However, caution must be exercised when comparing these studies due to variations in participant

demographics and backgrounds, as well as differences in the methodologies employed.

Despite being among the few studies globally to assess public knowledge regarding intravenous thrombolysis in AIS patients and early stroke symptoms, which is crucial for improving patient outcomes through enhanced awareness and reduced arrival times, this study possesses certain limitations. Firstly, its online nature may limit the generalizability of findings to individuals without internet access. Secondly, its cross-sectional design inherently restricts the depth of analysis. Lastly, the absence of a consistent, validated questionnaire for measuring public awareness and knowledge regarding stroke and intravenous thrombolysis in AIS patients represents a significant limitation.

In conclusion, while the overall knowledge of the Taif, Saudi Arabia general population concerning early stroke symptoms was deemed sufficient, deficiencies were noted in recognizing sudden blurred vision and sudden dizziness, difficulty in walking, loss of balance, or coordination. While a considerable proportion of individuals recognized thrombolytic agents as essential drugs for treating cerebral infarction, a significant percentage lacked awareness regarding the critical time window for their administration. Therefore, there is a pressing need to augment public knowledge on this vital matter through comprehensive health education programs in outpatient clinics and primary care centres. Additionally, conducting further population-based studies employing validated, specific questionnaires is recommended to deepen our understanding of this subject.

Expanding on these efforts, collaboration between healthcare providers, policymakers, and community organizations could facilitate the dissemination of accurate information and promote proactive measures to improve stroke awareness and response rates in Saudi Arabia. By leveraging various communication channels, including social media platforms, educational campaigns, and community outreach programs, stakeholders can empower individuals to recognize stroke symptoms promptly and seek timely medical intervention, thereby mitigating the burden of stroke-related morbidity and mortality in the region.

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